

Impact of microfinance on the operations of small business enterprise in rural areas

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Abstract

The growth rate of farmers' income is relatively slow, and the income gap between urban and rural residents and regions continues to enlarge. The problems of agriculture, rural areas, and farmers are still serious in China, which needs to pay more attention to system innovation and reasonable policy adjustments. This study aims to determine the impact of microfinance on the asset scale, annual sales, annual net profit, and number of employees of small enterprises in rural areas. The hypothesis of the study would reveal if microfinance played a positive role in promoting the development of small rural enterprises. The researcher divided the overall sample into two groups: one group was the experimental group, that is, the enterprises that obtained bank loans (including general commercial banks and rural cooperative banks for about 60% of the total sample), and the other group was the control group, the enterprises that did not obtain any bank loans. A panel-data model was used to analyze the role of corporate lending on performance. A comparative study found that experimental and control groups after one year differed in the following factors: size of the assets, net profit, sales, fixed assets accounted for, possession of the land, enterprise, intangible assets, and age. Results show that bank loans have a significant positive impact on the performance of sample enterprises, such as the size of fixed assets, asset scale, net profit, and the number of employees, while non-bank loans have a certain difference in the performance of different indicators and even have a certain negative effect on some performance indicators. The government should strengthen policy guidance to help small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) strengthen their ability to resist risks and obtain loans, constantly innovate the financial system, and increase financial supply according to the change in their financial needs. This will promote the production increase of enterprises and the sustainable development of rural economies.

Keywords: Microfinance; Operations; Small business enterprise; Rural areas.

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Introduction

China, as a big agricultural country, has always been a major issue related to the development of the national economy and modernization. China's national economy has made great progress since the reform and opening up, but rural development is still beset with difficulties. At present, the growth rate of farmers' income is relatively slow, and the income gap between urban and rural residents and regions continues to enlarge. The problems of agriculture, rural areas, and farmers are still serious in China, which needs to pay more attention to system innovation and reasonable policy adjustments.

Rural finance is an important part of modern finance. As an important capital factor allocation system in rural economic development, rural finance plays an increasingly significant role in rural economic

development. Microfinance is not only an important way of alleviating poverty but also an innovation in financial services. The service target of microfinance is mainly the low-income class in urban and rural areas. By providing financial services to low-income farmers or rural microenterprises, the income of farmers or microenterprises can be increased, and the development of the rural economy can be promoted. Microfinance is the result of the continuous innovation of traditional financial service means. As a financial poverty alleviation method, microfinance is widely welcomed in less developed countries and regions.

Due to the adjustment of the state's financial policy, major businesses considering profit maximization from rural financial institutions market's withdrawal (only the rural financial network as absorbing rural savings institutions), including lack of farmers and rural small and medium-sized enterprise credit services have no real improvement. In order to realize the stable development of agriculture and the continuous increase of farmers' income, it is necessary to improve the rural financial service, increase the supply of rural credit and goods, and provide financial guarantee for the development of the rural economy, which has become the consensus of theoretical research and practitioners.

Despite years of China's rural financial system, China also saw rapid development. For a long time, China formed a typical urban-rural dual economic structure of the industrial sector's financial policy orientation, leading urban areas to rural financial repression. Existing rural financial development still cannot meet the needs of a multi-level, diversified rural economy. As a special financial service, rural microfinance has been developed very quickly in China and has become an innovative financial service to help the poor. Through years of practice, rural credit cooperatives have accumulated some experience in the publicity of the role of rural small loans, loan issuance, and management, but there are still many problems in the development process of rural small loans to be solved and improved.

Financial development plays an extremely important role in capital accumulation and economic growth. Since Mckinnon (1993) and Shaw (1973) opened up the field of financial development and financial deepening, it has attracted the interest of many economists and has been continuously supplemented, revised, and developed in the following two decades. In developing countries, increasing farmers' income and improving the welfare level of rural communities have always been the focus of the government. The correct system design and appropriate policies will not only bring better results but also achieve possible results in the aspects of system derivation and self-sustainable development. The new method of rural finance changes the traditional method of injecting low-priced credit funds. It suggests that the government should play a more active role in establishing a reasonable policy environment to promote the smooth operation of the rural financial market.

Scholars at home and abroad have done a lot of research on the financing of farmers and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). In the rural areas of developing countries, credit constraints are generally considered to be the key factor hindering economic growth and the improvement of rural residents' living standards. Starting from the classical enterprise financing theory, scholars have conducted in-depth tests and positive corrections on the financing needs of SMEs, which has gradually developed the theories related to the financing needs of SMEs.

Theoretical Framework

As an important part of small and medium-sized enterprises in rural areas, with the continuous improvement of the market economy and of the industrial level, despite the outstanding rural problems, the construction and development of small and medium-sized enterprises in rural areas have been gradually put on the agenda. However, the definition of small and medium-sized enterprises in rural areas, although there is a unified definition of small and medium-sized enterprises, is too general and not fully applicable to rural small and medium-sized enterprises. According to the judgment of small and medium-sized enterprises in terms of absolute scale and standards to characterize rural small and medium-sized enterprises, economic development in our country is unbalanced lead to a different degree of development of rural enterprises in

various regions, where the judgment standard in various regions is often different. Therefore, we regard all enterprises other than large-scale enterprises in rural regions in our country as rural small and medium-sized enterprises, but also including small and micro non-agricultural activities which are not formally registered in the industry and commerce sectors.

The study of rural small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) is defined as: layout in county towns, diversification of investment, to develop the country's economy as the main task, relatively large-scale enterprises of all enterprises as the rural small and medium-sized enterprises, including those not officially registered small and micro non-agricultural activities in the Ministry of Commerce and Industry. This concept should contain the following elements: first, from the perspective of the investment body, the rural collective economic organization or farmer investment is the main; second, from the perspective of regional characteristics, mainly located in rural areas; third, from the investment purpose, to undertake the obligation of supporting agriculture; fourth, from the perspective of labor source, enterprises mainly absorb rural surplus labor; fifth, from the production scale, mainly in rural areas, belong to the larger enterprises outside the enterprise. Therefore, rural small and medium-sized enterprises, mainly rural collective economic organizations or farmer investment, undertake the obligation to support agriculture and absorb the rural surplus labor force of small enterprises, including rural township collective enterprises, individual and private enterprises, and other small and medium-sized enterprises.

The Theory of Rural Finance Promoting Rural Economic Growth

As an important part of overall financial development, rural finance is inevitably affected by modern financial development theory and its policy propositions. In the field of rural finance in developing countries, there are three different theories, namely agricultural subsidies theory, rural financial market theory, and credit theory. In recent years, with the rise of information economics and the imperfect competition market theory, from the point of its viewpoint and policy proposals, the three schools, respectively, corresponding financial restraint theory, theory of financial deepening, and financial constraint theory and policy proposals.

Agricultural subsidy credit theory. Before the 1980s, the agricultural subsidy credit paradigm was the dominant traditional theory in the field of rural finance. The implicit presupposition of this paradigm is that the rural residents, especially the poor class, do not have the ability to save, and the rural areas are faced with a chronic shortage of funds. Moreover, because of the industrial characteristics of agriculture, it is impossible for commercial banks to take profit as the object of financing. To increase agricultural production and alleviate rural poverty, it is necessary to inject policy funds from outside rural areas and establish non-profit, specialized financial institutions to allocate funds.

Theory of rural financial markets. In the 1980s, the rural financial market paradigm gradually replaced the agricultural subsidy credit paradigm. The theory of rural financial markets emphasizes the role of market mechanisms and puts forward the following policy propositions: first, the main function of financial institutions is to function as financial intermediaries within rural areas, and the mobilization of savings is the key. Second, in order to mobilize savings and balance the supply and demand of funds, the interest rate must be determined by the market mechanism. The third is to judge whether the success of rural finance should be based on the results of financial institutions (capital intermediary volume) and their management of self-reliance and sustainability; fourth, there is no need to implement the system of lending to specific targets; and fifth, informal finance is reasonable to a certain extent. It should not be completely abolished, but both formal and informal financial markets should be used.

Imperfectly competitive market theory. After the 1990s, it was recognized that to foster efficient financial markets, social and non-market elements were still needed to support them. Stiglitz and Weiss' (1981) incomplete market paradigm provides some theoretical support for this understanding. Its basic framework is that the financial market of developing countries is not a perfectly competitive market,

especially since the lender cannot fully grasp the situation of the borrower. If the market mechanism is completely relied on, it may not be able to cultivate the financial market needed by society. To remedy market failures, non-market elements such as appropriate government involvement in financial markets and the organization of borrowers are necessary. The government should adopt an indirect control mechanism to supervise the financial market and establish the scope and standard of supervision according to certain principles.

Foreign research on rural finance in developing countries can be represented by the comprehensive research report of the World Bank. The report targets rural finance in two areas: increasing income to promote economic growth and reducing poverty (Yaron, 1994). But recent research suggests that microfinance, which features subsidies, does not have much of an impact on poverty reduction and, instead, creates a new moral hazard. The report also analyzed the reasons for the inefficient operation of rural financial markets, believing that the main reasons are an improper policy environment, inadequate legal and regulatory systems, and market failure. The performance evaluation framework of rural financial institutions proposed by Yaron (1992) has been widely accepted by academics and practitioners. The framework includes two basic indicators: target customer coverage and the sustainability of rural financial institutions. The former is a mixed indicator used to evaluate market penetration and the quality of services provided. It can measure the extent to which rural financial institutions successfully serve their target customers and meet their demand for financial services. This index is both qualitative and quantitative and can measure both depth and breadth.

Statement of the Problem

1. What are the assets and liabilities of the interviewed enterprises?
 - 1.1 Total fixed assets
 - 1.2 Total variable assets
 - 1.3 Total current liabilities
 - 1.4 Total long-term liabilities
2. What are the financing channels and amount of surveyed enterprises?
 - 2.1 Enterprise's own funds
 - 2.2 Commercial bank loans
 - 2.3 Rural cooperative bank loans
 - 2.4 Government investment
 - 2.5 Private Lending
3. What is the impact of microfinance on the asset scale, annual sales, annual net profit and number of employees of small enterprises in rural areas?

Hypothesis

- H1: Microfinance plays a positive role in promoting the development of small rural enterprises.
H2: Microfinance plays a negative role in hindering the development of small rural enterprises.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The scope of this study includes the impact of microfinance on the asset size, annual sales, annual net profit, and number of employed employees of small enterprises in rural areas. First, this study is aimed at small rural enterprises. Different countries and regions have different definitions of small enterprises, but they are basically defined by the scale of the enterprise, including annual sales, the number of employees employed, and total fixed assets. The classification standards of small enterprises involved in this paper are

implemented in accordance with the Regulations on the Classification Standards of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (No. 300 [2011]) issued by the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology, the National Bureau of Statistics, the National Development and Reform Commission, and the Ministry of Finance (Dezan Shira & Associates, 2011). Second, given that China has a typical urban-rural dual economic structure, the findings of this study on small enterprises in rural areas may not be applicable to all kinds of enterprises in urban areas. Third, this study only deals with the field of microfinance in corporate financing and does not deal with other fields of corporate financing behavior.

Research Design

There are many ways to finance small enterprises. Among all kinds of external financing channels, bank loans are one of the most important. Strengthening the analysis of the availability of SME loans and its influencing factors is of great significance for formulating an effective SME financing system to alleviate the financing constraints of SMEs. The survey data of small and medium-sized enterprises is used to analyze the availability of bank loans and influencing factors of the sample enterprises, which are divided into an experimental group and a control group by the experimental economics method, and the performance of rural small and medium-sized enterprise bank loans.

In fact, the analysis of the factors affecting the availability of bank loans to small and medium-sized enterprises is also to study the factors affecting the estimation of bank loans to small and medium-sized enterprises. From the perspective of the sources of various influencing factors, it can be roughly divided into the following three types: enterprise characteristic factors, bank characteristic factors, and macro-economic and social environments. In fact, these three factors affect the bank's willingness to lend by affecting the transaction cost, capital cost, and credit contract execution cost of the bank's capital supply. In the study, since the sample enterprises are all in the same social and economic environment and facing the same financial market, we mainly focus on the characteristics of enterprises, including their mortgage guarantee ability, ownership form, business scale, profitability, credit rating, and intangible assets. By comparing the characteristics of enterprises that have obtained bank loans and those that have not obtained bank loans, this paper analyzes the most important enterprise characteristic factors that affect the enterprises ability to obtain loans.

Enterprise Asset Scale

If the enterprise can provide a sufficient mortgage or find a third party to guarantee its loan, it may increase the incentive of credit contract execution for the enterprise so as to reduce the risk of default and make the bank get certain compensation after default. Some empirical studies can indirectly prove that collateral or guarantees can help reduce the requirement for information symmetry between banks and firms. While measuring a firm's ability to provide collateral, the firm's assets, especially fixed assets, are a common choice. Bopaiah's (1998) analysis of US data shows that a firm's total asset level has a significant positive impact on improving its bank lending conditions. Studies by Berger et al. (2015) and Peek and Rosengren (2016) reached similar conclusions. But other studies have found the opposite. D'Mello and Toscano (2020) find that firms with larger assets are more likely to take out expensive business credit, which in part means they are less likely to get credit.

However, due to the large number of small and medium-sized enterprises concentrated in the service industry and the difference in growth strategies between large enterprises and small and medium-sized enterprises, the proportion of fixed assets in the total assets of small and medium-sized enterprises is very low, which means many small and medium-sized enterprises often do not have the ability to provide mortgages. In this case, seeking a third-party guarantee is a better choice. The form of guarantee can be a mutual guarantee between enterprises or a third-party professional guaranteed institution. The advantage of

the third party's ability to grasp the information of the borrower can reduce the bank's information search cost. In this study, the scale of assets, the proportion of fixed assets, the form of land occupied by the enterprise, profitability, and other variables are used as proxy variables to reflect the ability of the enterprise to provide a mortgage guarantee.

Form of Ownership of Enterprises

Most of China's SMEs are non-public enterprises, and the current banking system is dominated by the state. For fear of being accused of losing state-owned assets, state banks are usually reluctant to lend to non-state SMEs. Brandt and Li's (2003) analysis of Chinese data found that private companies have less access to bank loans and that when they do get loans, they typically receive them on higher collateral terms and in smaller quantities, suggesting that China's state-owned banking sector does have an ownership discrimination problem, resulting in a shortage of loans to private SMEs. However, in recent years, with the gradual completion of the shareholding reform of state-owned banks and the entry of more shareholding commercial banks and non-bank financial institutions led by private capital in the county financial market, whether such discrimination in forms of ownership still exists needs to be further tested.

Transparency of Corporate Information

Compared with large enterprises, SMEs are at a relative disadvantage in the ability to improve their own "hard information," so there is information asymmetry between banks and enterprises in the ability and willingness to repay loans. The information asymmetry between lenders and borrowers will lead to adverse selection and moral hazard problems, so banks may adopt credit rationing strategies, which will affect the financing availability of enterprises. The indicators used by scholars to measure the transparency of corporate information are also different, including the age of the enterprise and relationship banking. This study intends to use corporate credit rating, intangible assets (the number of national, provincial, and municipal honorary titles) and other indicators as proxy variables for corporate information transparency.

Other Factors

The characteristics of the capital demand of enterprises will also affect the willingness of banks to supply loans. A company's sales or sales growth rate is usually a good indicator of the level of capital demand (Petersen & Rajan, 2002). Using data from the World Bank, Beck (2013) found that firms with larger sales were less likely to face financing barriers, and the effect of this variable was highly statistically significant. In addition to the above factors, the enterprise's previous lending record, the industry in which the enterprise is located, the geographical location and the actual distance from the bank, as well as the relationship characteristics between the owner and the bank's credit officers, will also affect the bank's loan supply willingness by affecting the bank's transaction costs and the degree of information asymmetry.

Respondents of the Study

Rural small enterprises engaged in agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, fishing, industry, construction, wholesale, retail, accommodation, catering, and other seven industries were selected to issue questionnaires. The selection criteria for small enterprises are: the operating income of agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry and fishery enterprises is 5 million yuan or less; An industrial enterprise with less than 300 employees and an annual operating income of less than 20 million yuan; The operating income of the construction enterprise is 60 million yuan or less, and the total assets are 50 million yuan or less; The number of employees in the wholesale business is 20 or less, and the operating income is 50 million yuan

or less; The number of employees in the retail industry is 50 or less, and the operating income is 5 million yuan or less; The number of employees in the lodging industry is 100 or less, and the operating income is 20 million yuan or less; Catering enterprises have 100 employees or less, and the operating income is 20 million yuan or less.

In the process of investigation, we divided the overall sample into two groups: one group was the experimental group, that is, the enterprises that obtained bank loans (including general commercial banks and rural cooperative banks, for about 60% of the total sample), and the other group was the control group, the enterprises that did not obtain any bank loans. The experimental group is a stratified random sample divided according to the number of employees and the scale of assets. The experimental group is also divided into two subsample groups: one group is the enterprises that have received loans from general commercial banks (accounting for 20% of the experimental group), and the other group is the enterprises that have received loans from rural cooperative banks.

The enterprise characteristic variables selected in this study are mainly divided into the following four categories:

1. The scale of enterprise assets or the ability to provide mortgage and guarantee. The asset scale uses the total assets in the financial statements of the enterprise as the proxy index. There are two ways for enterprises to occupy land: transfer or lease. When they occupy land in the form of a transfer, land can be used as collateral to apply for bank loans, while when they occupy land in the form of a lease, land cannot be used as collateral. When setting specific variables, if the variable is occupied in the form of a transfer, it is equal to 1, otherwise it is 0. The rate of return on total assets is equal to the total profit before interest and tax/the average total assets x 100%. The higher the index is, the better the asset utilization efficiency of the enterprise and the stronger the profitability of the whole enterprise.

2. Forms of ownership. In rural SMEs, there are fewer state-owned enterprises, so such samples could not be obtained in the survey. The main forms of ownership of the sample enterprises are divided into the following three categories: collective enterprises, private enterprises, and foreign-funded enterprises, which focused on the comparison of different ownership of enterprises in different groups based on the proportion of distribution.

3. Transparency of corporate information. Select enterprise age, intangible assets, and credit grade as its proxy index. Intangible assets are represented by the following variables: whether the enterprise has its own registered trademark (yes=1, no=0), and the number of honorary titles of each level obtained by the enterprise. Credit rating variables are assigned as follows: AAA = 1, AA = 2, A = 3, and not participating in credit rating = 4.

4. Other factors. It mainly includes the sales volume of the enterprise and whether it has obtained bank loans in the previous year to reflect the characteristics of the enterprise's capital demand and its previous borrowing record. In addition, this paper also adds two indicators representing the movable property of enterprises: the proportion of inventory in total assets and the proportion of accounts receivable in total assets. About 60% of the total assets of small and medium-sized enterprises in China are accounts receivable, and inventory and movable property are very limited.

Research Instrumentation

Based on the research of Ashenfelter and Card (1984), Heckman and Hotz (1989), and Hanousek et al. (2009), we use the Panel-data model to analyze the role of corporate lending on performance. The specific model is as follows:

$$\ln X_{ijt} = \alpha_i + (\beta_j) L_{ijt} + (\gamma_j) X_{ijt} + (\theta_j) L_{ijt} + (\phi) D_t + v_{ijt}$$

In the model, X_{ijt} is an index representing the performance of an enterprise in the year t , where subscript i represents the sample enterprise j represents the loan type obtained by the enterprise. L_{ij1} is set as dummy variable if enterprise I obtains loan in year t , the value is 1; otherwise, it is 0; D represents the dummy variable that measures the year effect. The key variable is L_{ijt} , and its coefficient θ_j reflects the effect of loan on enterprise performance. In addition, it uses α_i to control the time-invariant factors of different enterprises in 2020-2021 uses L_{ij1t} to control the role of bank and non-bank loans before 2020 uses X_{ij1t} to control the lag role of enterprise performance before 2020 and the role of year change φ .

Results

Table 1. The impact of bank loans on the size of fixed assets of small and medium-sized enterprises

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T Statistic	Probability
Constant	3.749412	0.295034	12.70840	0.0000***
Fixed assets in 2020	0.000093	0.000021	4.386609	0.0000***
Whether there is a bank loan dummy variable *t	0.000586	0.000161	3.640234	0.0003***
Whether there is a non-bank loan dummy variable *t	0.000288	0.000152	1.896691	0.0593*
Dummy variable (2021)	0.000196	0.000185	1.056221	0.2921
Loan dummy variable in 2020	0.577974	0.446388	1.294780	0.1968
R-squared	0.210920	F-statistic		11.11963
Adjusted R-squared	0.191952	Prob (F-statistic)		0.000000
Observations	214			

Note: ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is significant at 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively.

Table 2. The influence of bank loan on the asset scale of small and medium-sized enterprises

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T Statistic	Probability
Constant	5.284175	0.247091	21.38554	0.0000***
Assets in 2020	0.000076	0.000013	5.746076	0.0000***
Whether there is a bank loan dummy variable *t	0.000465	0.000135	3.445352	0.0007***
Whether there is a non-bank loan dummy variable *t	0.000216	0.000127	1.700557	0.0905*
Dummy variable (2021)	0.000296	0.000155	1.910268	0.0575*
Loan dummy variable in 2020	0.600523	0.378918	1.584837	0.1145
R-squared	0.271717	F-statistic		11.11963
Adjusted R-squared	0.254210	Prob (F-statistic)		0.000000
Observations	214			

Note: ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is significant at 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively.

Table 3. The influence of bank loan on the annual net profit of small and medium-sized enterprises

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T Statistic	Probability
Constant	-77.90479	114.5466	-0.680115	0.4972
Net profit for 2020	1.243453	0.139861	8.890667	0.0000***
Whether there is a bank loan dummy variable *t	0.176497	0.062558	2.821307	0.0052***
Whether there is a non-bank loan dummy variable *t	0.069534	0.058950	1.179536	0.2395
Dummy variable (2021)	0.063777	0.071946	0.886457	0.3764
Loan dummy variable in 2020	-293.1389	176.9769	-1.656368	0.0992*
R-squared	0.314076	F-statistic		19.04808
Adjusted R-squared	0.297587	Prob (F-statistic)		0.000000
Observations	214			

Note: ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is significant at 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively.

Table 4. The impact of bank loans on the number of annual employees of small and medium-sized enterprises

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T Statistic	Probability
Constant	-11.08416	21.50290	-0.515473	0.6068
Number of employees at the end of 2020	0.966425	0.070178	13.77106	0.0000***
Whether there is a bank loan dummy variable *t	0.031804	0.011610	2.739357	0.0067***
Whether there is a non-bank loan dummy variable *t	-0.006002	0.010927	-0.549281	0.5834
Dummy variable (2021)	0.040990	0.013452	3.047240	0.0026***
Loan dummy variable in 2020	-36.05007	32.29437	-1.116296	0.2656
R-squared	0.505734	F-statistic		42.56519
Adjusted R-squared	0.493853	Prob (F-statistic)		0.000000
Observations	214			

Note: ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is significant at 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively.

Table 5. The impact of bank loans on annual sales of small and medium-sized enterprises

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T Statistic	Probability
Constant	-1403.062	3352.532	-0.418508	0.6760
Sales in 2020	1.326364	0.125294	10.58598	0.0000***
Whether there is a bank loan dummy variable *t	3.233094	1.829693	1.767015	0.0787*
Whether there is a non-bank loan dummy variable *t	-1.405371	1.722226	-0.816020	0.4154
Dummy variable (2021)	2.823414	2.105185	1.341172	0.1813
Loan dummy variable in 2020	-4387.221	5073.115	-0.864798	0.3881
R-squared	0.369674	F-statistic		24.39763
Adjusted R-squared	0.354522	Prob (F-statistic)		0.000000
Observations	214			

Note: ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is significant at 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively.

The results of empirical analysis are listed in Tables 1–5, and the model results are all obtained through panel least squares. Bank loans have a positive impact on the scale of fixed assets, asset scale, net profit, and number of employees of sample enterprises, and all of them are statistically significant at the 1% level. The average effect is about 0.06%, 0.05%, 17.65%, and 3.18%, respectively. Bank loans also

have a positive impact on the annual sales of the sample enterprises, which is significant at the 10% statistical level.

Similarly, non-bank loans also have a significant positive impact on the scale of fixed assets and the assets of enterprises, both of which are statistically significant at 10%. They also have a positive impact on net profit, but they fail to pass the significance test. However, the model results show that the impact of non-bank loans on the number of employees and sales of enterprises is negative, although not significant. From the perspective of loan performance, although non-bank loans have the advantage of easy access compared with bank loans, due to the relatively high financial cost of non-bank loans, their impact on the performance of different indicators of enterprises has a certain difference and even a certain negative effect.

Therefore, it can be found that, after controlling for some factors that may affect enterprise performance, bank loans have a significant positive impact on the performance of rural SMEs in counties. Due to the relatively low financial cost brought by loans and the good stability of obtaining loans, the role of bank loans is greater than that of non-bank loans. Non-bank loans also have a positive impact on corporate performance, but generally speaking, the impact is neutral. The hypothesis of this study is whether microfinance will negatively hinder or positively promote the development of small enterprises in rural areas. Through data research, it can be seen that microfinance plays a positive role in promoting the development of small rural enterprises.

Discussion

This study uses the financing survey data of rural SMEs to analyze the factors affecting enterprises' access to loans and the performance of enterprises' access to bank loans. First of all, the enterprises that obtained bank loans and those that did not were divided into the experimental group and the control group, respectively. A comparative study found that the test group and control group after one year differed in terms of the size of the assets, net profit, sales, fixed assets accounted for and possession of the land, the enterprise in the form of intangible assets, and age. There are large differences between enterprises: the bigger the enterprise, the more intangible assets it has, the ability to provide mortgages, and the age of the enterprise to obtain them, the higher the risk of bank loans. After further discussion, we find that the "soft information" between banks and enterprises still plays a very important role in the current financing system of rural SMEs in the county. The role of "soft information" is obviously more important than that of "hard information." Meanwhile, credit ratings can play a positive role in the process of enterprises getting loans.

Secondly, it analyzes the degree and direction of bank loans on the business performance of sample enterprises, including the scale of assets, the number of employees, profits, fixed assets, and investment. The results show that bank loans have a significant positive impact on the performance of sample enterprises, such as the size of fixed assets, asset scale, net profit, and the number of employees, while non-bank loans have a certain difference in the performance of different indicators and even have a certain negative effect on some performance indicators.

Conclusion

Financial demand is the foundation for the establishment of the financial system. The structure, quantity, and characteristics of financial demand determine the structure and function of the financial system to a considerable extent. With the development of the rural economy and the promotion of market-oriented reform, rural financial demand is constantly changing, and the change in financial demand in turn has an impact on the evolution of the rural financial system and system innovation. Therefore, the analysis of financial demand is the foundation of the study of rural financial problems.

This study focuses on the rural financial demand level based on microcosmic perspective econometric methods of lending to farmers in less developed areas and their welfare effects. Empirical studies using field survey data analysis examine the influence factors of rural small and medium-sized enterprise financing in developed regions and the influence of credit investment on its productivity. Through theoretical and empirical analysis, the following main conclusions are drawn:

There is still a certain amount of financial repression in rural and underdeveloped areas. Both formal and informal lending play an important role in the production and business activities of farmers. Since the non-farm income of farmers is difficult to guarantee for them to obtain loans from financial institutions, formal financial institutions need to strengthen product innovation, fully explore effective mortgages, and guarantee information to create new financial products to meet the borrowing needs of farmers and reduce the risks in their loans.

Small and medium-sized enterprises in rural areas and developed areas contribute greatly to local economic development. The proportion of equity financing in small enterprises is much higher than that in large enterprises, while the proportion of debt financing is lower. With the expansion of enterprise scale, the proportion of capital obtained from big banks gradually increases, while the proportion of capital obtained from small banks gradually decreases, which indirectly verifies the view that local small and medium-sized banks can play a greater role in solving the financing of small and medium-sized enterprises. The higher the credit rating, the higher the proportion of debt financing. The lower the credit rating, the higher the proportion of equity financing. Rural small and medium-sized enterprises have a relatively strong demand for capital; the most important problem is the lack of liquidity.

Enterprises that obtained bank loans and enterprises that did not obtain bank loans in 2021 were divided into an experimental group and a control group, respectively. The study found that experimental group and control group in one year are the size of the assets, net profit, sales, fixed asset ratio, occupy land, enterprises in the form of intangible assets, and age. There are large differences between enterprises: the bigger the enterprise, the more intangible assets it has, the ability to provide mortgages, and the older the enterprise is to obtain them, the higher the risk of bank loans. Soft information between banks and enterprises still plays an important role in the financing system of small and medium-sized enterprises in rural counties. The bank loan has a significant positive effect on the performance of the sample enterprises, such as the size of fixed assets, the size of assets, the net profit, and the number of employees.

In the current rural financial market, farmers and rural SMEs face more serious credit rationing, and it is difficult to obtain credit support from regular financial institutions. The main reason, on the one hand, is that the majority of farmers and rural small and medium-sized enterprises, due to a lack of collateral, face a “natural” financing bottleneck. On the other hand, due to the height of the rural financial market monopoly and fully using the traditional formal financial institutions, commercial loans simply use traditional lending mechanisms, which will make the most of the farmers and rural SMEs who cannot get credit. Therefore, it is necessary to innovate in the aspects of rural financial markets and operation mechanisms.

Recommendations

In view of the above conclusions, the government should strengthen policy guidance to help SMEs strengthen their ability to resist risks and obtain loans, constantly innovate the financial system, and increase financial supply according to the change in SMEs’ financial needs, so as to promote the production increase of enterprises and the sustainable development of rural economies.

1. Guide rural SMEs to improve their own level and enhance their loan capacity. In all countries, more than 99 percent of companies are classified as SMEs. The enterprise in the upper part of the pyramid can be either in the capital market for financing or from the middle of the bank loan to the

small and medium-sized enterprises. The credit holder is the customer that the bank is chasing and also has the channel to enter the capital market. By financing constraints, there are tens of millions of micro and small enterprises at the bottom of the pyramid, especially those whose history is short and small, with generally no formal financial statements to be the basis of analysis of bank loans. They also cannot meet the requirements of the bank for traditional guaranteed conditions such as real estate collateral. Therefore, small and medium-sized enterprises, in order to obtain loan support, must strive to find market positioning to improve their competitiveness. First of all, we must have a good credit concept to carry out production and financing activities in accordance with the law and pay back the principal and interest on loans on time to establish a good image of keeping faith and performing the contract. Secondly, efforts should be made to improve the level of financial management. To establish and improve the enterprise financial system according to law, enterprises should increase the transparency of financial information, strengthen internal financial management, facilitate the supervision and management of banks, and reduce loan risks. Third, we should improve the level of enterprise management. We should gradually improve the corporate governance structure of enterprises to establish a business management mode to meet the needs of the market economy and continuously enhance the production capacity of new products and their risk-resistance ability to enhance their market competitiveness.

2. Innovate financial products and loan guarantee methods according to the characteristics of rural SMEs' capital needs. The main rural commercial banks should continue to push for reform to improve the credit management system and financial services. On the premise of preventing risks, we should take effective measures to increase the credit supply to rural small and medium-sized enterprises to support the development of the rural economy, set up a marketing department for small rural enterprises to study, formulate, supervise, and implement relevant policies and measures to support the development of small rural enterprises, improve the existing credit rating system and credit eligibility criteria, establish a credit rating and credit granting system for rural small enterprises, and timely meet the reasonable capital needs of rural small enterprises with credit, good benefits, and increased employment. Enterprises should innovate financial service rules and develop new business rules or financial tools suitable for the financing and settlement needs of rural small enterprises. They should improve the loan marketing constraints and incentive mechanism to encourage grassroots banks and credit officers to actively conduct credit marketing to simplify loan approval procedures and formulate comprehensive assessment methods scientifically and reasonably for credit officers to grant and recover loans.

At the same time, innovative loan guarantee methods expand the scope of effective collateral. The enterprise must encourage financial institutions according to the characteristics of the agricultural and rural economic development pilot area in accordance with the relevant legalities that further expand rural enterprises to apply for a loan that can be used to guarantee property scope, actively regulate and perfect the agricultural guarantee loan business operation process, and establish and improve the agricultural loan guarantee mechanism of property assessment, management, and disposal. In accordance with the principle of adapting measures to local conditions and being flexible and diverse, the mortgage loans of large agricultural production equipment, forest rights, and the right to use four wildlands with clear ownership and controllable risks, and the pledge loans of accounts receivable, warehouse receipts, transferable equity, patent rights, and trademark exclusive rights shall be conducted according to law. In cases where they do not violate the provisions of the current law, property rights can effectively control risk and can be used for all kinds of movable and immovable property loan guarantees. Pilot can be used for loan guarantees to actively promote and perfect the rural credit guarantee system. The construction of diversified credit guarantee institutions encourages all kinds of credit guarantee institutions with the combination of large financing guarantee services for rural areas.

3. Establish a reasonable financing guarantee risk compensation mechanism for rural SMEs. Rural small and medium-sized enterprises have a large number, wide distribution, and complex structure of the economic group; rural small and medium-sized enterprise guarantee institutions face more complex factors. In the absence of risk compensation mechanisms at present, rural policy guarantee institutions have

generally appeared to have the problem of negative expansion of the industry, and it is difficult to guide social funds into the financing guarantee field of rural SMEs. It can be seen that up-to-risk compensation is an essential operating mechanism for the sustainable development of guaranteed institutions. The Promotion Law of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises clearly stipulates that “*the central budget should set up the subject of small and medium-sized enterprises to support the development of special fund. Local people’s governments should provide financial support to small and medium-sized enterprises in light of the actual situation.*” Therefore, both central and local finance should support the development of small and medium-sized enterprises in accordance with the law.

Second, increase financial supply and reduce credit rationing in rural financial markets. Because of the prevalence of financial repression, finance is the main factor restricting the development of the rural economy, which is a common understanding in theoretical circles. On type judgment about the financial repression, generally think that even if there were some inhibition phenomena, the main or inhibition performance in China’s rural, direct reason is that farmers and rural small and medium-sized enterprises find it difficult to get loans from the formal financial institutions. The problem nature is embodied in due to the functional defects existing in the current rural financial system that led to the low efficiency of rural financial supply. Therefore, financial institutions should timely launch financial services that meet the needs of rural areas, reduce credit rationing in rural financial markets, and play the role of rural finance in promoting the production increase of rural enterprises and farmers’ incomes, so as to promote the development of the rural economy.

1. Vigorously cultivate all kinds of micro rural financial institutions. Research shows that the proportion of equity financing in small enterprises is much higher than that of large enterprises, while the proportion of debt financing is lower. With the expansion of enterprise scale, the proportion of funds obtained from large banks gradually increases, while the proportion of funds obtained from small banks gradually decreases, indicating that local small and medium-sized banks can play a greater role in solving the financing of small and medium-sized enterprises. Therefore, on the premise of strengthening supervision and preventing risks, we should adjust and relax the market access policy of banking financial institutions in rural areas, accelerate the development of various forms of regional small and medium-sized banks mainly serving rural areas, encourage and guide qualified domestic and foreign financial, industrial, and private capital to invest and set up various types of new rural financial institutions in rural areas, such as village banks, agricultural loan companies, and rural mutual funds cooperatives, carry out commercial operations, and serve the production of farmers and small and medium-sized enterprises. In order to further improve rural financial market competition and operational efficiency, it is important to encourage financial institutions to support various types of banks in setting up branches in rural areas so as to improve and increase the coverage of rural financial institutions and further activate the rural financial market.

2. Actively innovate rural capital supply and return mechanism. To guide the return of funds, the most fundamental way is to solve the income of funds. Therefore, governments at all levels and relevant departments shall be formulated, including fiscal, tax, monetary policy, a package of economic policy and regulatory policies, guide the rural capital flow, introduce the regulations of the State Council as soon as possible, and create new rural areas deposits on the local measures for supervision and inspection of the financial institutions. In order to establish rural capital forced return mechanism, commercial banks can directly invest or deposit funds to rural financial institutions to increase their capital strength in two ways. The regulatory authorities implement classified supervision for rural financial institutions under the unified supervision benchmark so as to improve the effectiveness of supervision. For example, in the supervision of the capital adequacy ratio, regulatory standards become lower. In this way, the policy force of funds supporting agriculture will be formed, and the profit-driven policy will guide the financial capital to tilt toward the economy, improve the hematopoietic function, and support the healthy development of the rural economy. Second, the financial department should make the existing financial funds for agriculture support a part of the loan discount interest funds, guarantee funds, and agricultural support risk funds through farmer loans and county rural small and medium-sized enterprise loans, discount interest to support, and leverage

commercial finance to three agriculture credit interventions. Tax authorities shall implement preferential policies of exempting business tax and reducing income tax for agriculture-related loans of all financial institutions and guide financial institutions to operate in rural areas. Third, the central bank should give agriculture-related lending institutions priority in terms of relending, rediscounting, financing in the financial market, preferential payment of deposit reserves, preferential interest rates, and other monetary policies.

3. Correctly guide the legalization of rural informal finance. Informal finance is born in the process of economic development, and it is not the product and transitional institutional arrangement of a specific stage, nor will it die out naturally with the development of the economy. Its existence has its inevitability and rationality. The government's crackdown may be more detrimental to economic development and social stability, and it is not the best choice to squeeze or replace informal finance with formal finance. Therefore, in order to make it compete directly with formal finance, it is necessary to reduce the market access conditions, guide its development, and make it a pole of the financial diversification strategy. Some illegal financial institutions, such as private banks with a certain amount of registered capital, which can operate in accordance with the law and have a high compliance rate, should be allowed to turn into legal private financial institutions within a certain period of time and be formalized. At the same time, we will rationally guide funds from the formal financial sector into the private credit market. Mortgages, pledges, commercial banks, and credit cooperatives provide loans to agricultural industrialization-leading enterprises and private enterprises, and then use their advantages to lend in private market information to stakeholders, microenterprises, rural farmers professional cooperatives, and agricultural service organizations such as groups to guard against moral hazards. This connection between private financial activities and formal finance can effectively increase financial supply, reduce transaction costs for rural financing, and achieve a win-win situation.

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